

Table 1. Germplasm use by the national program of Bolivia.

Year	Nurseries (no.)		Return (%)	Lines ^a (no.)	Varietal release		
	Dispatched	Returned			Number	Year of introduction	Time span (yr)
1979	7	3	42.9	256	0	-	-
1980	6	3	50.0	217	0	-	-
1981	9	7	77.8	201	0	-	-
1982	2	2	100.0	190	0	-	-
1983	1	1	100.0	30	0	-	-
1984	2	1	50.0	208	0	-	-
1985	2	0	0.0	111	0	-	-
1986	1	1	100.0	230	0	-	-
1987	1	1	100.0	179	2	1979/1981	8/6
1988	2	2	100.0	98	0	-	-
1989	3	3	100.0	137	0	-	-
1990	5	3	60.0	42	0	-	-
1991	6	1	16.7	101	0	-	-
1992	5	1	20.0	43	0	-	-
1993	3	2	66.7	74	2	1987/1987	6/6
1994					2	1988/1988	6/6
Total	55	31	-	2117	6	-	-
Av	3.7	2.1	56.4	141	0.4	-	6.3

^aBolivia evaluated 287 lines to release a variety. This average results from dividing the total number of lines introduced from 1979 (the year the line was introduced that gave rise to the first variety) to 1988 (the year the line was introduced that resulted in the most recently released variety) by the number of released varieties.

Table 2. Germplasm use by the national program of Ecuador.

Year	Nurseries (no.)		Return (%)	Lines ^a (no.)	Varietal release		
	Dispatched	Returned			Number	Year of introduction	Time span (yr)
1982	9	1	11.1	409	0	-	-
1983	6	2	33.3	411	0	-	-
1984	65	2	33.3	373	0	-	-
1985	6	2	33.3	336	0	-	-
1986	3	2	66.7	381	1	1982	4
1987	5	0	0.0	290	0	-	-
1988	5	0	0.0	217	0	-	-
1989	8	3	37.5	235	1	1986	3
1990	7	0	0.0	94	0	-	-
1991	3	0	0.0	214	0	-	-
1992	1	0	0.0	157	0	-	-
1993	5	0	0.0	84	0	-	-
1994					1	1990	4
Total	64	12	-	3201	3	-	11
Av	5.3	1.0	18.8	267	0.2	-	3.7

^aEcuador evaluated 915 lines to release a variety. This average results from dividing the total number of lines introduced from 1982 (the year the line was introduced that gave rise to the first variety) to 1990 (the year the line was introduced that resulted in the most recently released variety) by the number of released varieties.

commercial variety, with an average of 3.7 yr elapsing between introduction and release.

Bolivia tested 2,117 introductions from 55 nursery sets and released six varieties from 1979 to 1994. The national program evaluated an average of 287 lines per variety released, with an average of 6.3 yr between introduction and release.

Bolivia thus tested only one-third of the total lines evaluated by Ecuador to release a variety but required twice as much time to achieve the same result. These results may

be attributed to differences in the national programs' breeding strategies, target ecosystems, financial resources, and stability of breeder positions.

In conclusion, the two national programs have efficiently used germplasm distributed through INGER-LAC. If efficiency is measured as the time from introduction to release, Ecuador is more efficient than Bolivia. But if the main criterion is the number of lines evaluated to release a commercial variety, then Bolivia is more efficient than Ecuador. ■

Distribution of ribosomal DNA polymorphism in wild and cultivated rice from China

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Chinese rice comprises a major portion of the world's rice gene pool. The objective of this study was to gain understanding of the level and distribution of genetic diversity in Chinese rice germplasm using ribosomal DNA (rDNA) spacer length polymorphisms as markers.

We surveyed three sets of rice: a sample of 83 accessions of *Oryza rufipogon* that represented most of its ecogeographical range; a sample of 348 entries of cultivated *O. sativa*, including both indica and japonica varieties from almost all rice-growing areas in China; and 50 accessions of both indica and japonica cultivars from South and East Asia. Sampling emphasis was also given to a well-recognized center of diversity for cultivated rice (Yunnan in southwestern China) and to areas identified as being historically important for rice cultivation and evolution.

Statistics pertinent to levels of rDNA polymorphisms were summarized (see table). In all, 42 spacer length variants (slvs) were resolved in samples of 481 accessions. These slvs comprised a stepladder, with step sizes varying from 21 to 311 bp. Thirty-six of 42 slvs were observed in *O. rufipogon*, but only 15 slvs were detected in *O. sativa*, despite it having more accessions than *O. rufipogon*. Nine slvs occurred in both *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa* samples, and one of them was observed at a predominantly high frequency in both *O. rufipogon* (0.310) and *O. sativa* (0.428). This slv probably represents a widely adapted allele at one of the rDNA loci.

Summary statistics of rDNA polymorphisms in wild and cultivated rice.

Sample	Wild	Cultivated			Total
		Total	Indica	Japonica	
Spacer length variants (no.)	36	15	14	13	42
Phenotypes (no.)	40	48	36	28	80
Diversity	2.99	2.57	2.33	2.38	2.85
Sample size (no.)	83	398	228	170	481

All six slvs occurring in *O. sativa* but not in *O. rufipogon* were rare ($f < 0.01$). In contrast, all of the slvs but one occurring in both *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa* were observed at much higher frequencies ($f > 0.02$) in *O. sativa*. A majority of the 27 slvs occurring only in *O. rufipogon* were infrequent or rare ($f < 0.02$), but a few of them were detected at sizeable frequencies (0.025-0.095). Overall, no drastic difference existed in the composition of slvs between *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa*. About equal numbers of slvs were observed in indica and japonica samples. However, distribution of slvs is clearly differentiated between indica and japonica rice groups: indica rice is preferentially associated with longer slvs and japonica rice with shorter ones. Furthermore, indica rice is dominated by one slv, whereas, in japonica rice, two common slvs were observed at about equal frequencies.

The combination of slvs observed in an accession is called a phenotype. Eighty phenotypes, made up of the 42 slvs, were observed in the total sample; the composition of the phenotypes varied from one-banded (containing only one slv) to six-banded, with the one-banded type being the most common. In contrast to the slvs, it is surprising that more phenotypes were observed in *O. sativa* than in *O. rufipogon*. The phenotype occurring most frequently in the *O. rufipogon* group was also observed with highest frequency in *O. sativa*. However, only a few phenotypes were common between *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa*. More phenotypes were detected in indicas than in japonicas. While all of the phenotypes occurring at frequencies more than 0.01 were observed in both indica and japonica groups, these groups differed substantially in phenotypic composition.

In summary, our analysis established that common wild rice is much more diverse in rDNA slvs than is cultivated rice, but cultivated rice has more slv combinations than does wild rice. This indicates that recombination, functioning to assemble various slvs into individual varieties, has played an important role in the evolution of cultivated rice. This observation might have some implications in resolving a recurring issue concerning the relative amount of genetic variation in wild and cultivated species. It is well recognized that the cultivated forms are usually phenotypically more numerous than their wild relatives, which leads many to believe that cultivated species contain more genetic variation than their wild relatives. The reverse had been argued with the availability of data from molecular marker analyses.

More slvs (presumably with correspondence to alleles) with fewer phenotypes in the wild species compared with fewer slvs with more phenotypes in the cultivated species, as observed in this study, might explain the contrasting patterns in phenotype and DNA diversity of wild and cultivated species. ■

A research program for on-farm conservation of rice genetic resources

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More than 75,000 accessions of cultivated *Oryza sativa* are stored in the International Rice Genebank at IRRI, thus ensuring their security and continued availability for rice improvement. However, from an evolutionary point of view, this ex situ conservation is static: the adaptation of stored varieties to the biotic and abiotic environment is frozen. Thus, in addition to efforts toward genebank efficiency, research is needed on a complementary approach to ex situ conservation.

On-farm conservation is dynamic and aims to promote adapting genetic resources by using the evolutionary processes that

created the diversity of rice varieties. On-farm conservation of crop genetic resources is defined as the continued cultivation and management of a diverse set of crop populations by farmers in the agroecosystems where a crop has evolved.

Despite increasing interest in on-farm conservation, knowledge on the meaning of this approach is still limited. Before implementing on-farm conservation, we need improved knowledge of its driving force: farmers' management of diversity.

Our research program for on-farm conservation started in April 1995 with funding from the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation. The objective is to identify opportunities to involve farmers' managed systems in the conservation of rice genetic resources. To accomplish this, we will study the management of rice diversity by farmers and its genetic implications.

We have used two theoretical planning frameworks (Figs. 1 and 2). Our research will address the socioeconomic, socio-cultural, environmental, and genetic aspects of farmers' management of diversity. We will also study farmers' management of diversity and its consequences using several combinations of factors that can influence diversity: market interaction (low/high), ethnic origin of farmers (minority/majority), and environmental heterogeneity (low/high) (Fig. 1).

We will pay particular attention to within-variety genetic polymorphism, which is the basis of evolutionary changes. The findings will lead us to assess other sources of genetic diversity (Fig. 2). The focus will be on the rainfed lowland ecosystem where the co-occurrence of modern and traditional varieties is expected. Study locations will be in India, Philippines, and Vietnam.